

Brand Orientation and Performance Synergies in Indian MSMEs - A SEM Exploration

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Abstract:

Purpose: “This study examines the MSME (micro, small, and medium enterprise) sector in India to determine the correlation between brand orientation, brand performance, and company performance, focusing on MSMEs in four major cities of Gujarat. While these findings provide significant insights into the MSME sector, the geographic limitation suggests a need for further research to generalize the results. Additionally, future research should explore external factors, such as market dynamics and competitive pressures that may influence brand orientation and performance synergies.

Design/Methodology/Approach: This research used structural equation modeling (SEM) to examine the correlations among variables, drawing on a sample size of 690 businesses. This study analyzes the brand orientation of micro, small, and medium-sized enterprise (MSME) owners and managers in four major Gujarati cities: Surat, Vadodara, Ahmedabad, and Rajkot. To guarantee a strong response rate, the data gathering process used electronic channels and personalized methods.

Findings: A brand-centric attitude is critical to an organization's success, as the research found a substantial and statistically significant positive association between brand orientation and brand performance. The research also reveals a strong positive correlation between brand success and company performance. Antecedents such as organizational resource, organizational structure, and organizational culture foster brand orientation within MSMEs.

Limitations/Implications: While the study provides valuable insights into MSMEs in Gujarat, the geographic limitation to four major cities in Gujarat (Surat, Vadodara, Ahmedabad, and Rajkot) restricts the broader applicability of the findings. A more diverse sample, including MSMEs from different regions across India or other countries, would help generalize the results and provide a more comprehensive understanding of brand orientation and performance synergies in MSMEs.

Conclusion: Emphasize the value of exploring further external factors such as market conditions and expanding the research to other regions.

Originality/Value: This study provides important insights for both academics and practitioners in the Indian business environment by pioneering the analysis of the underexplored relationship between brand orientation, brand performance, and company success within the MSME sector in India.”

Keywords : Brand Orientation, Brand Performance, Business Performance, MSMEs, SEM

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1. Introduction

The importance of a strong brand in today's cutthroat business environment is paramount. Brands are priceless because they sum up a company's core values and connect with customers in competitive markets. Businesses place a high monetary value on their brands because they are among their most valuable assets [1]. Brands are living, breathing things that can change how people think about a company, how they buy its products, and how successful that company is.

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A brand is more than just a logo or slogan; it represents the whole range of an organization's character, including its principles, goals, and the promise it makes to its customers. At the heart of this paradigm is the idea of brand orientation, a mentality shift that elevates the brand to the status of both a commodity and a foundational element of the company's identity. A compelling brand image, a brand-centric culture, and a brand-centered management structure are the three pillars upon which this paradigm shift rests. According to academics [2], brand orientation is the level of alignment between a company's marketing plan and the brand, highlighting the brand's profound and revolutionary character.

Even though branding is important for many different types of businesses, it becomes even more crucial for MSMEs.

These businesses operate in highly competitive and ever-changing marketplaces, where they often face limitations in terms of available resources. Effective branding is a strategic need, not an extravagance, for small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs). According to the source [3], effective brand management plays a critical role in a small business's ability to stay afloat by providing a competitive advantage and encouraging resilience when confronted with market obstacles. The ancient saying goes something like, "small businesses with big brands." It says that brand orientation may help small firms stand out, make customers loyal, and deal with the complexities of today's business world.

Our study aims to examine the complicated linkages among brand orientation, brand performance, and overall company performance in the context of this interaction between brand orientation and business dynamics. Our study seeks to shed light on the strategic role of branding by exploring the various aspects of brand orientation and how it affects various organizational aspects. This research will be especially useful for micro, small, and medium-sized businesses (MSMEs) that are trying to thrive in a market where brands play a pivotal role.

2. Material and Methods

2.1 Area of Work: Textile Industry

This study aims to focus on how product differentiation capability in the textile MSMEs (micro, small, and medium enterprises) enhances their brand orientation and brand performance. This study uses a strong structural equation modeling (SEM) technique to investigate the complex effects of brand-centric initiatives on company performance and brand recognition. This study aims to shed light on the unique possibilities and threats that micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs) encounter in Gujarat by concentrating on four major cities: Surat, Vadodara, Ahmedabad, and Rajkot. The overall goal of this study is to shed light on the specific challenges faced by Indian micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs) and how best to address them through improved brand management techniques and the encouragement of long-term success."

2.2 Measurement Development

As part of the effort to develop reliable measuring instruments, we carefully adjusted the chosen scales to guarantee cultural relevance and response accuracy. We carefully translated thirteen items into Gujarati and Hindi from [4] to enhance respondents' understanding without compromising the validity of their answers. Unfortunately, there was a lack of a relevant scale in the literature about brand performance. The research addressed this gap by utilizing a four-item scale, previously designed for consumer markets [5]. Notably, renowned academics collaborated to revise the scale's items to suit the complex circumstances of this research. Similarly, the study's objective necessitated the operationalization of financial success using a four-item scale that had been previously developed [6], with adjustments made in conjunction with academic specialists to conform to the study's specifics.

Figure 1: Factors Influencing Brand Orientation and Their Impact on Brand and Business Performance

2.3 Sampling and data collection

Managers and owners of MSMEs in the Surat, Vadodara, Ahmedabad, and Rajkot areas made up the study's sample. Deliberate exclusion of persons in lower hierarchical levels ensured a broad organizational strategy viewpoint. The study employed Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) through the Smart-PLS program, and utilized a non-probabilistic technique to determine the sample size. We found a diversified pool of 800 enterprises by employing snowball sampling and convenient sampling, all of which met the MSME requirements set by the Government of India. Owners and managers were intentionally spotlighted due to their policymaking and strategic decision-making responsibilities. We made this strategic decision to enhance the accuracy and reduce bias in the answers gathered for the study's variables. We disseminated the poll via electronic means such as WhatsApp, email, and targeted social media group posts. We sent a link to the survey and a detailed cover letter explaining its aim to people who might be interested in participating in the research. After three rounds of reminders, 690 businesses responded strongly. We used a personalized strategy to encourage respondents to take the survey in person, in addition to our internet outreach. This dual-method technique significantly enhanced the response rate, mostly generated through these channels. Despite the high response rate, the analysis phase excluded 37 replies due to incorrect questionnaire completion.

2.4 Hypothesis Development

2.4.1 Brand Orientation and Brand Performance

Market share, brand equity, customer loyalty, and financial results are all components of a multifaceted concept of brand performance [7]. When a brand does well, it shows that it is effective in the market. Promoting a favorable image of the brand helps build trust and loyalty among consumers [8]. Happy and committed consumers are more likely to produce better brand performance indicators. Consistent brand communication across all touchpoints is a hallmark of brand-oriented organizations [9]. Consistent branding is linked to positive brand performance results. Brand orientation is

essential to staying ahead of the competition, innovating branding tactics, and responding to changing market conditions [10]. Brand innovations often lead to improved brand performance. Better brand representation in the market is the internal result of an organization's emphasis on building a loyal and passionate brand among its workers [11]. Employee support enhances a brand's success.

H1: There is a positive relationship between brand orientation and brand performance

2.4.2 Brand Performance and Business Performance

The brand's success may have a significant impact on the company's bottom line. When we talk about a brand's performance, we mean how well it meets its objectives and adds value to the company. Business performance, on the other hand, takes into account the entity's total profitability and success. Many studies have shown that there is a direct correlation between how well a brand does and how well a company does financially. Research [12] highlights the importance of brand performance in shaping customer perceptions and loyalty. When consumers have faith in and are satisfied with a brand, it boosts the company's bottom line. As noted in [13], the strength of the brand influences both customers' preferences and the company's financial performance. Increases in market share are often associated with better brand success, according to studies like [14]. The performance of a brand greatly influences the building of consumer loyalty. According to [15], creating an emotional connection between customers and a well-perceived brand leads to increased repeat business and favorable word-of-mouth. Multiple studies have shown that repeat business is an important factor in a company's long-term success [16]. Companies that have built up significant brand equity are in a better position to charge premium pricing and make more money, according to [17].

H2: "There is a positive relationship between brand performance and business performance

2.4.3 Antecedents of brand orientation

2.4.3.1 Resource abundance and brand orientation"

Having an excess of resources is a key factor that drives organizations to focus on their brand, as mentioned before [18]. According to this model of strategic management, a company's operational emphasis should be on its brand rather than traditional marketing. Here, the resource-based view [19], which looks at an organization's assets, is crucial. The availability and purposeful use of internal assets and capabilities are crucial to establishing brand orientation. Brand competence, or high-order competency, combines various resources to increase brand value. There is empirical evidence that companies can't completely commit to brand orientation unless they have a lot of resources. To help cultivate a brand-oriented attitude, businesses can strategically use their resources and concentrate on differentiating their products [20]. Organizations that want to succeed in today's ever-changing markets must understand the interdependence of abundant resources and brand orientation if they want to maintain a competitive edge.

H3: "There is a positive relationship between Resource abundance and Brand Orientation"

2.4.3.2 Long Term Remuneration and Brand Orientation

Staff incentives can influence a company's dedication to brand-building initiatives, which in turn can influence long-term compensation structures and brand orientation. Long-term compensation often takes the form of incentive programs linked to longer performance periods to align workers' interests with the organization's long-term success [21]. By ensuring everyone aligns with the brand, a brand-oriented organization instills values in its culture and practices [22]. According to the research [23], employees are more likely to feel invested in the company's success and take pride in their work when they have a clear path to long-term financial gain. As a result, this has the potential to improve brand orientation by inspiring workers to represent the brand in all their dealings, both within and outside of work [24]. Organizations may cultivate a steady and educated staff that is familiar with brand ideas via long-term compensation plans, which can help retain employees [25]. Staff members who care about the company's future are more inclined to passionately advocate for the brand. On the other hand, compensation gaps could stymie brand orientation initiatives if employees lack investment in the company's long-term success [26]. Staff members may be less invested in living up to the company's ideals if they feel their efforts aren't paying off in the long run.

H3: "There is a positive relationship between Long Term Remuneration and Brand Orientation

2.4.3.3 Organizational Identification of members and Brand Orientation

Organizational identification, the process by which people associate themselves with an organization, can greatly impact brand orientation techniques. Research provides a basic understanding of organizational identification by highlighting the mental and emotional connections people have with their jobs. When people have a strong sense of belonging to the organization, they are more inclined to embrace and promote its brand [27]. Research [28] favorably impacts both internal and external brand consistency with a brand-oriented organizational culture. People who feel a sense of belonging to the company are more likely to adhere to the brand's principles, thereby fostering a brand-focused culture [29].

H4: There is a positive relationship between Organizational Identification of members and Brand Orientation

2.4.3.4 Product Differentiation Capability and Brand Orientation"

Brand orientation and product differentiation capabilities are in constant motion with one another, and this dynamic synergy is critical in determining how a company stands out in the market. As previously stated, product differentiation capability refers to a company's ability to make items that are different from the competition and stand out in the market. An organization's capacity to innovate, develop better

features, and provide more value to consumers is the foundation of this competency [30]. On the other hand, brand orientation refers to the coordination of an organization's internal operations and external communications to establish and uphold a strong brand identity [31]. It involves creating an environment where the organization's focus is on the brand. The capacity to differentiate one's products from the competition is the bedrock of a memorable brand. A memorable and recognizable brand is built on items that are unique and distinctive [32]. On the other side, when a brand is well-established, consumers identify it with higher quality and more value, which helps a company's products stand out from the competition [33].

H5: There is a positive relationship between Product Differentiation Capability and Brand Orientation

2.4.3.5 Organizational Structure and Brand Orientation

As stated in [34], an organization's structure includes the formal allocation of tasks, positions, and connections among members of the organization. Multiple configurations are possible, including centralized, decentralized, hierarchical, and matrix-based models. In order to establish and sustain a strong brand identity, it is important for all members of the organizational ecosystem to work together in harmony with the brand's fundamental principles, which is what brand orientation is all about [35].

These two factors have a complex interaction. A centralized organizational structure ensures consistency between departments and functions, potentially leading to more consistent and managed brand messaging [36]. According to research, a consistent brand strategy is easier to execute in an organization with a well-defined structure [37]. A brand-centric culture may flourish when company goals are aligned with the brand's [38]. On the other hand, localized brand strategies may be possible with a decentralized structure's increased adaptability and flexibility [39]. A fractured or mismatched structure may lead to brand communication inconsistencies and identity dilution [40].

H6: There is a positive relationship between Organizational Structure and Brand Orientation

3. Results

3.1 Structural Equation Modelling

One statistical tool for delving into the intricate webs of interactions between study variables is structural equation modeling, or SEM. The measurement model assesses the dependability and accuracy of the measured variables, whereas the structural model delves into the connections between hidden variables. In a structural equation modeling (SEM) study, we refer to the unobservable theoretical notions as latent constructs and use the observable variables as indicators or measurements of these constructs.

The structural equation model (SEM) can measure the organizational performance of companies. The model's constructs include "brand orientation," "brand performance," "business performance," "long-term remuneration,"

"organizational identification of members," "organizational structure," "product differentiation capability," and "resource abundance." These structures represent different parts of the organization's operations. Using SEM, researchers may assess the measurement features of their data and test complicated theoretical models all at once, which helps them understand the phenomena they are studying by revealing the correlations between variables and their underlying structure.

3.1.1 Reliability and Validity of the Model

Table 1 - Reliability and Validity of the Model

Construct	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Brand Orientation	0.949	0.95	0.955	0.622
Brand Performance	0.923	0.924	0.94	0.722
Business Performance	0.913	0.934	0.938	0.792
Long Term Remuneration	0.914	0.918	0.94	0.796
Organizational Identification of members	0.89	0.904	0.916	0.648
Organizational Structure	0.841	0.843	0.887	0.611
Product Differentiation Capability	0.897	0.906	0.929	0.767
Resource Abundance	0.816	0.818	0.879	0.646

With "Cronbach's alpha values ranging from 0.816 to 0.949, all structures in the SEM model show strong levels of internal consistency. Items within each construct consistently measure the same underlying notion, since these values are above the universally recognized criterion of 0.7 [41]. This proves that all of the components in each construct are the same and reliably measure the target construct.

- Composite Reliability (rho_a and rho_c): Composite reliability is a better metric than Cronbach's alpha for assessing the internal consistency dependability of SEM constructs. Within each construct, rho_a and rho_c values evaluate how consistent things are. With rho_a and rho_c values ranging from 0.818 to 0.955, all constructs in the model demonstrate strong levels of dependability in terms of internal consistency. The constructs are internally trustworthy and the observed variables correctly measure the latent constructs, since these values meet the suggested threshold of 0.7.
- Average Variance Extracted (AVE): All of the constructions in the SEM model show good variance

extraction, with AVE values between 0.611 and 0.796. Each construct explains a significant amount of the variation in its measured items compared to measurement error, since these values are more than 0.5. This provides support for the hypothesis that the model's constructs accurately reflect the theoretical ideas behind them and that the observed variables adequately account for the variation in those constructs.

- Construct Validity: Composite reliability (rho a and rho c), AVE, and Cronbach's alpha all show high values, which means the concept validity and internal consistency are good. These results strengthen the validity of structural equation modelling (SEM) by providing evidence that the observable variables are reliable indicators of the underlying latent components.”

3.2 Discriminant validity

We must ensure discriminant validity in a structural equation model (SEM) to guarantee construct distinctiveness. If the diagonal values in the correlation matrix are higher than the correlations for brand orientation, brand performance, business performance, long-term pay, organisational identification, organisational structure, product differentiation capability, and resource abundance, then the Fornell-Larcker criterion (FLC) is met. Furthermore, all HTMT ratios (below.85) confirm discriminant validity, which further supports the uniqueness of the constructs. This thorough evaluation strengthens faith in the SEM's dependability and the study's resilience.

Table 2 - HTMT Ratio

	Heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT)
Brand Performance <-> Brand Orientation	0.813
Business Performance <-> Brand Orientation	0.416
Business Performance <-> Brand Performance	0.416
Long Term Remuneration <-> Brand Orientation	0.528
Long Term Remuneration <-> Brand Performance	0.54
Long Term Remuneration <-> Business Performance	0.241
Organizational Structure <-> Brand Orientation	0.699
Organizational Structure <-> Brand Performance	0.766
Organizational Structure <-> Business Performance	0.336
Organizational Structure <-> Long Term Remuneration	0.823
Organizational Structure <-> Organizational Identification of members	0.789
Product Differentiation Capability <-> Brand Orientation	0.544
Product Differentiation Capability <-> Brand Performance	0.548
Product Differentiation Capability <-> Business Performance	0.207
Product Differentiation Capability <-> Long Term Remuneration	0.768
Product Differentiation Capability <-> Organizational Identification of members	0.782
Product Differentiation Capability <-> Organizational Structure	0.814
Resource Abundance <-> Brand Orientation	0.611
Resource Abundance <-> Brand Performance	0.615
Resource Abundance <-> Business Performance	0.223
Resource Abundance <-> Long Term Remuneration	0.662
Resource Abundance <-> Organizational Identification of members	0.785
Resource Abundance <-> Organizational Structure	0.813
Resource Abundance <-> Product Differentiation Capability	0.799

4.3 Hypothesis Testing

Structural equation modelling (SEM) hypothesis testing looks at how important the correlations between constructs are by using the calculated coefficients, standard errors, and sample size. If there are statistically significant correlations between the constructs, we may learn about them using the T statistics and p-values. Brand Orientation and Brand Performance are strongly and statistically related ($|O/STDEV| = 0.698/0.083 = 8.411, p < 0.001$). The link between brand performance and business performance is positively and significantly correlated ($|O/STDEV| = 0.372/0.088 = 4.234, p < 0.001$).

Table 3 - Results of Hypothesis Testing

	Original Sample (O)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Brand Orientation -> Brand Performance	0.698	0.083	8.411	0
Brand Performance -> Business Performance	0.372	0.088	4.234	0
Long Term Remuneration -> Brand Orientation	0.07	0.047	1.474	0.141
Organizational Identification of members -> Brand Orientation	0.198	0.055	3.624	0
Organizational Structure -> Brand Orientation	0.559	0.06	9.296	0
Product Differentiation Capability -> Brand Orientation	0.05	0.058	0.863	0.388
Resource Abundance -> Brand Orientation	0.225	0.041	5.464	0

There is statistical support for the hypothesis that members' organizational identification, organizational structure and resource abundance are determinants of brand orientation. The connections between these variables and brand orientation are robust and statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), as shown by the T statistics of 3.624. There is no statistically significant correlation between brand orientation and long-term compensation or product differentiation capability.

The SEM results show a robust correlation between brand orientation and brand performance. However, the findings are limited to MSMEs in Gujarat, and future studies should examine how external variables like market competition and

digital transformation might affect the brand orientation-performance link in different contexts.

4. Conclusion

According to this study, brand orientation and brand performance have a strong and positive relationship. This is in line with what is already known in the literature, which showed that brand orientation has a direct and positive effect on brand performance. Further research validates these findings, emphasizing the intrinsic link between a brand-oriented mindset and brand success [7]. The link between brand performance and company performance is now the center of attention in the research." The research highlights the critical significance of brand performance in impacting customer perceptions and loyalty, and the found positive association aligns with previous studies. Furthermore, as noted in [1], a strong brand can affect a company's bottom line by influencing customer tastes and preferences. Thus, our research adds to the larger conversation by demonstrating how important it is to have a strong brand in order to have a successful company.

The study that explores the antecedents of brand orientation identifies organizational structure, resource availability, long-term pay structures, product differentiation capabilities, and organizational identity of members as key elements. This research confirms what is already known in the literature, most notably the seminal study on the importance of many resources in building brand loyalty [36]. In addition, the research agrees with [21] on the complex relationship between brand orientation and long-term compensation systems. Organizational identity, a fundamental driver of brand orientation (as explained in [5]), highlights the significance of workers identifying with the organizational brand. Consistent with views expressed in [30, 31], the research bolsters the interdependent nature of product differentiation capacity, organizational structure, and brand orientation.

4.1 Originality of the study

The novel aspect of this research is the way it investigates the interplay between brand orientation, brand performance, and company performance in India's MSME sector. The study fills a significant gap in the literature by providing research on this topic, particularly in relation to MSMEs. This study breaks new ground by investigating the dynamics of brand management as it pertains to the unique possibilities and threats encountered by smaller businesses in India, a field that has received very little attention from academics. Recognizing and addressing the varied business settings within the nation, the study's regional specificity—conducted in Surat, Vadodara, Ahmedabad, and Rajkot—further improves its unique contribution. In addition to enhancing our general knowledge of brand and company success, this research provides useful regional insights for companies with operations in these areas.

4.2 Future Research Scope

Future studies should investigate the impact of external

factors such as market conditions, competitive intensity, and the role of digitalization on brand orientation in MSMEs. Expanding the sample size to include MSMEs from other regions or sectors could provide broader insights. Additionally, examining cultural and regional variations across India or in international contexts will help validate the findings and provide more nuanced strategic recommendations.

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